

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Pyruvic Acid by Ce(IV) Sulphate

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In the oxidation of pyruvic acid by Ce(IV) sulphate in presence of different acidities, the order of the reaction has been found to be 1 after about 2 min. The activation energy and entropy of activation have been calculated to be 11.0 ± 1 kcal./mole and -28.1 ± 2.0 (e.u.) respectively. The effect of salts on the reaction velocity has also been studied.

Fromageot and Desnuelle¹ determined pyruvic acid by adding it to a solution of ceric sulphate in $N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and back-titrating after 5 minutes with a solution of Mohr's salt. These workers did not study the kinetics of the oxidation reaction. In the present communication the results of such kinetic studies have been recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pyruvic acid (L. R. variety) was purified by distillation² under reduced pressure (b.p. $60\text{-}62^\circ/10$ mm) and estimated by acid/alkali titrations. Other reagents were prepared as described earlier³. pH adjustments were made in H_2SO_4 (dil.) and measurements were carried out in a Cambridge bench type pH-meter, calibrated against a standard buffer.

Solutions of pyruvic acid and ceric sulphate, taken in separate 250-ml pyrex conical flasks, were kept in a thermostat for sometime and then were rapidly mixed. Aliquots of the mixed solution were withdrawn after definite intervals and analysed for ceric ion by the iodometric method.

The amount of ceric ion consumed per mole of pyruvic acid was estimated by the usual method after keeping ceric salt solution 10 times in excess of the acid in the thermostat at 25° for 24 hours. One mole of pyruvic acid was found to require two equivalents of ceric sulphate. The oxidation product was found to be acetic acid, confirmed by the cacodyl oxide reaction.

Oxidation of pyruvic acid was studied with about two-fold excess of ceric salt. The plot of $\log (a/a-x)$ against ' t ' (a and $a-x$ have the usual significance) is linear, indicating that the reaction is of the first order. The first-order velocity constants have been calculated from the slope of the $\log (a/a-x)$ vs. t plot.

1. *Biochem. Z.*, 1935, 279, 174.

2. Ball, "Biochemical Preparations", Vol. II, p. 22, 1950, John Wiley and Sons, New York.

3. Sengupta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 823.

Effect of pH on the Reaction Velocity.—The experiments were performed at different pH values. The curve $\log K$ against pH is linear within the limits studied (Table I, Fig. 1). The slope is nearly unity, indicating that the rate is inversely proportional to $[H^+]$ in H_2SO_4 .

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Salt Effect on the Reaction Velocity.—Two different salts, such as $MgSO_4$ and Na_2SO_4 , were added to the reaction mixture, the proportion of pyruvic acid and ceric salts being in the ratio of 1:2. Both Na_2SO_4 and $MgSO_4$ were found to retard the rate of oxidation (Table II).

TABLE I

Oxidation of pyruvic acid by ceric sulphate at different acidity.

No.	[Pyruvic acid].	[Ceric sulphate].	Temp.	pH.	$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹).
1	0.01250M	0.0250M	15°	1.28	4.30
2	0.01370	0.0302	"	1.26	4.05
3	0.00625	0.0147	"	1.02	3.26
4	0.00937	0.0220	"	0.98	3.34
5	0.01370	0.0302	5°	1.26	1.97
6	"	"	"	1.12	0.92
7	"	"	"	1.02	0.905

TABLE II

Oxidation of pyruvic acid in presence of salts.

[Pyruvic acid] = 0.0137M, [Ceric sulphate] = 0.0302M, pH = 1.26, Temp. = 5°.

No.	Salt and conc.	$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹).
1	Nil	1.970
2	4N Na_2SO_4	1.381
3	M $MgSO_4$	1.842

Influence of Temperature on the Reaction Velocity.—The reaction velocities were

measured at three different temperatures (Fig. 3). The results are recorded in Tables III and IV. All the three experiments were performed at identical pH. Log K was plotted against $1/T$ (Fig. 2) from which the activation energy was calculated as 11.0 ± 1 kcal., the corresponding $-\Delta S$ value being 28.1 ± 2.0 (e.u.).

TABLE III

Oxidation of pyruvic acid at diff. temp.

Conditions same as in Table II.

Temp.	...	15°	5°	0°
$K \times 10^2$ (min ⁻¹)	..	4.05	1.97	1.38

TABLE IV

[Pyruvic acid] = 0.0125M. [Ceric sulphate] = 0.0250M. pH = 1.28.

Temp.	..	15°	8°	0°
$K \times 10^2$ (min ⁻¹)	..	4.300	2.303	1.152

DISCUSSION

Pyruvic acid on oxidation with ceric sulphate provides acetic acid, two equivalents of ceric ion being used up per mole of the acid. In connection with the oxidation of pyruvic acid with chromic acid, Westheimer⁴ has observed that pyruvic acid undergoes oxidation much more readily than decarboxylation. That in the present oxidation process two equivalents of ceric ions are consumed per mole indicates absence of decarboxylation, otherwise decarboxylation would lead to the formation of acetaldehyde, which in its turn would have needed more ceric ions.

α -Keto-acids are known to be partially hydrated in aqueous solution⁵. The hydrated form of pyruvic acid possibly reacts with ceric ion and the oxidation takes place in the following manner;

4. *Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 45, 419.

5. Strehlow, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1962, 66, 302.

The first-order consumption of ceric ion can be explained on the basis that a steady state of free radical concentration is attained and this reacts with ceric ion to provide the final products. The effect of addition of salts and also the acidity can be explained on the assumption that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ is the reacting species and the ceric ions are present in solution as different complex species^{6,7}.

In rapid radical reactions⁸, it is found that the activation energy is small (<15 kcal.) and lies far below the energy required to dissociate chemical bonds involved (60-100 kcal.). Again, non-radical processes show large negative values of ΔS , but radical reactions have the values of ΔS in between -20 and -36 (e.u.). Experimental observation is in agreement with this

The author wishes to thank Prof. B. N. Ghosh, D. Sc., F. N. I. and Dr. S. Aditya, M.Sc., Ph.D. for their interest in the work and also to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a research grant.

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Received August 7, 1963.

6. Hardwick and Robertson, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1951, 29, 818, 828.

7. Jones and Sopper, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 802.

8. Walling, "Free Radicals in Solution", p. 39, 1957, John Wiley and Sons.